

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF NIGERIA AGIP OIL COMPANY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AMONG THE OGBA PEOPLE OF RIVERS STATE

¹Professor Deekor, I. Holly, ²Dr. Chidinma Dokubo and ³Ataye Susan Ededeh

Article Info

Keywords: community, corporate social responsibility, sustainable development, community sustainable development

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.19218879

Abstract

This study investigated the corporate social responsibility of the NAOC for sustainable development among the Ogba people of Rivers State. The main purpose of the study was translated into three specific purposes, three research questions, three corresponding hypotheses to guide the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study population consisted of 718 members of the Ogba people in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The entire population of 718 members of the Ogba people was used as the sample because it was a manageable size for research of this magnitude. The researcher's designed structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts. Two of the experts from the Department of Adult Education and Community Development and one expert from the Field of Measurement and Evaluation, all from Rivers State University. Cronbach's alpha reliability method was computed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science version 24.0 to obtain a coefficient of 0.76, which was used to test the reliability of the instrument. Of the 718 copies distributed, only 653 copies were retrieved and properly filled, which constitutes approximately 91% of the distributed copies. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypotheses at a p-value of 0.05. The major findings revealed that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on education, agriculture, and infrastructure contributes to sustainable community development to a high extent. The findings also revealed no significant difference in the mean rating of Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom,

¹Department of Adult Education & Community Development, Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria

²Rivers State University

³Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku, Rivers State, Nigeria

and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education, agriculture, and infrastructure contributes to sustainable community development. Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, it was recommended that Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu, through their stakeholders such as Community Development Committee members, youth bodies, and council of chiefs, should lobby to ensure that the subsequent CSR on education from oil firms within their environment focuses on areas that would enhance the extent of contributions to sustainable educational development among their communities.

Introduction

Every corporate business operates in an environment inhabited by people before, during, and after its business operations. This group of people, who are host of businesses, shares and pursues common values, objectives, and goals that make them referred to as a community. Charles (2016) described a community as a group made up of people living or working together with the same interest. Community is made up of people who share common attitudes, interests, and goals and work toward their goals. Consequently, community as an institution made up of people has a force that every corporate entity must consider it is to attain success in all its operations. Bearing in mind the significant roles of the community, corporate businesses need to establish and maintain a cordial relationship with their host community.

Oil companies, as corporate firms, understand the need for cordial relationship with their host communities; hence, they try to establish contact with relevant stakeholders through their CLOs. According to Victor (2021), the CLOs are mostly appointed by the communities or those called the landlords to inter-phase with the oil firms to ensure a cordial relationship between them and guarantee firms for smooth operations in return for certain community development projects. The Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC) is one of the many oil companies existing in Nigeria and Rivers State. In Rivers State, the NAOC is involved in offshore oil and gas exploration activities among the Ogba people in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA) (Kornom-Gbaraba & Aernan, 2021). NAOC operates many exploration stations across the Ogba people, specifically in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu. The activities surrounding this company's oil exploration come with attendant effects, in most cases, detrimental to the host communities and their inhabitants (Amadi, 2020). Consequently, the host communities expect the oil companies as their tenants to establish good corporate-community relationship through designing and implementing good CSR policies or programs in collaboration with their CLOs. James (2016) opined that since oil companies' facilities and employees reside in close proximity with their host communities and in some cases inside the communities, it is important that they develop CSR programme aimed at solving critical problems within the communities to engender peaceful atmosphere for their operations and the survival of today and future members of the community.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) policies or programme of firms are designed to provide certain interventions capable of reducing the suffering of people around them. Joe and Kechi (2013) described CSR as the policy and processes by which companies are guided to integrate social and environmental concerns in their business goals and objectives to show respect for the stakeholders and people whose environments have hosted them and ensure their sustainable business success. Mahoney and Roberts (2019) described corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a broad business concept detailing a company's desire to do business ethically. The United

Nations Industrial Development Organization (2024) described CSR as the focus of companies to take action and demonstrate sense of accountability to their operating and host environments in ethical ways. According to Hailsham, Dokubo, and Deekor (2021), corporate social responsibility when successfully implemented by companies improves, their image, strengthens their competitive advantage, and brings about positive effects on relevant stakeholders, such as customers, suppliers, and the community, hence providing the companies with a peaceful atmosphere for their continuous operations.

NAOC as a company is said to have developed CSR programs aimed at fostering corporate and community relationships for mutual development within its host communities (Masi, 2019). Agboghroma (2019) also noted that huge investments are made on social projects with direct or indirect effects on the host communities' development as part of NAOC's CSR. Similarly, Victor (2021) noted that the essence of NAOC's corporate social responsibility programs is to establish partnership for mutual progress, which will enhance business performance on the one hand and better community development on the other. Victor further noted that CSR actions for the benefits of the host communities connote partnership for development as advantages emanating from oil companies' benevolence seeing their business operations beyond profit making to include sustainable community building and development. Okere (2019) noted that issues surrounding sustainable community development are of paramount importance to NAOC as the company takes the present and future of the host communities very seriously. Okere further noted that the company has initiated different policies and programs as part of its corporate social responsibility. Such as using environmentally friendly chemicals for operations, education for women and youth empowerment, and improved physical infrastructure. Inferring from the foregoing, it is important to assess the views of the benefiting communities as to whether or not this CSR programs of NAOC have actually engendered sustainable development of various aspects of their communities.

Sustainable development implies development that focuses on addressing the current and future needs of the people. McMichael (2020) noted that sustainable development is perceived as development that meets the needs and aspirations of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This means that sustainable development should bring about sustainable advancement or sustainable progress to the beneficiaries, in this study's case, the community. Consequently, Arikawe and Taylor (2015) described sustainable community development as the use of natural or man-made resources in the community to meet the present and future needs of the people. Agboghrom (2019) noted that NAOC CSR is designed to deliver sustainable community development by providing improvements in education, agriculture, access to energy, good drinkable water, and other basic infrastructure. This means that the successful implementation of the NAOC CSR should bring about sustainable education, agricultural, and infrastructural development. These development strides would comply with Todaro's theory of development (1981), which states that to attain holistic development; development must not be viewed from one dimension but from a multidimensional perspective.

Sustainable educational development should promote equal access to quality education and training in culturally relevant curriculum areas to develop the manpower required for the continuous survival of institutions. Roorda (2019) noted that sustainable educational development efforts should ensure holistic, inclusive, and transformative education systems capable of empowering individuals to participate in strengthening communities and, contributing more to a sustainable and equitable world. This means that the NAOC CSR initiative on education should be able to guarantee equal access and transform community members for meaningful contribution to the environment's socio-economic sustainability.

Another aspect covered by NAOC CSR is agriculture. Sustainable agricultural development from the company's initiative should be able to provide people with practices and strategies to meet their current food and animal

production needs without compromising that of the future generation. Dan-Moller (2020) noted that this should lead to sustainable farming systems that use nontoxic and low-energy intensive processes yielding optimum production, productivity, and profitability. Alternative processes that are not toxic include the use of low-toxicity input or organic farming. The NAOC CSR agricultural initiative for host communities, known as the Green River Project (GRP), should be able to improve the crop propagation of the host communities' members, promote environments sustainability, improve the value of soil structure, and provide skills to host communities for sustainable food and protein production (NAOC, 2012).

Sustainable infrastructural development refers to the planning, design, construction, and management of physical infrastructure in a manner that meets present societal needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Drakakis-Smith (2021) noted that it involves integrating sustainability principles to areas such as resource-efficient buildings, water infrastructure, flood protection, good drainage systems, and proper waste management facilities. Sustainable infrastructural development enables the attainment of the other variables of sustainable community development referred to in this study. This is based on the fact that sustainable infrastructure provides support for attaining good and quality education, agricultural practices, health, and environmental and social-cultural issues. This means that where the infrastructure is absent or inadequate, the attainment of other aspects of sustainable community development can be very difficult; hence, the issue of sustainable infrastructure cannot be underestimated.

At this juncture, it is worth noting that many studies exist on oil companies' CSR and community development. For instance, Zhao (2015) investigated the content of the communication of leading Energy Corporation about CSR. Bagdasaryan (2016) also examined the current state of CSR implementation by oil companies in communities in Russia. Hailsham, Dokubo, and Deekor (2021) also examined the influence of CSR of Exxon Mobil, Nigeria unlimited on community development in Rivers State. Victor and Okpu (2021) also examined factors influencing host community perceptions and expectations of oil companies' corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices in the Niger Delta. Gbali, Weli, and Mmom (2021) also examined CSR and management of oil-related conflicts in South-South Nigeria. However, a cursory look at the existing studies revealed that none has assessed the NAOC corporate social responses and how they impact the sustainable community development of the Ogba people. This means that there is a gap in the literature with regard to this scope. Hence, the present study was conceived to fill the gap.

Statement of the problem

The essence of corporate social responsibility (CRS) as an important component of multinational companies operating in the oil rich region of the Niger Delta, specifically the Ogba Kingdom of Rivers State, cannot be overemphasised. This is because a robust CSR by oil companies such as Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC), which the Ogba kingdom is host to, addresses the numerous socio-economic and environmental challenges bedeviling the people such as youth unemployment, poverty, lack of economic opportunities, neglect due to lack of meaningful engagement, environmental degradation as a result of oil spillage and harmful industrial practices affecting farmlands, the aquatic system, and the overall health of the people and enhance their sustainable development. Taking this into cognizance, NAOC has claimed that it has implemented numerous projects through its CSRs, such as skilled training in micro-enterprise development and education scholarships to qualified members of the host communities, agricultural training and inputs provisions, road constructions, and improvement of educational facilities (Masi, 2019). A cursory look at the various projects NAOC had carried out through its CSRs revealed that they relate to the people's education, agriculture and infrastructural needs.

Nevertheless, the researcher is not sure whether NAOC's CSR efforts over the years have actually promoted sustainable development in the acclaimed areas where they were executed within Ogba communities.

In light of the foregoing stated problems relating to NAOC CSRs efforts, investigating the extent to which the efforts have promoted sustainable development within the Ogba communities by directly analyzing the opinion and view of the people as major stakeholders is necessary. The need for this investigation inspired this study.

Purpose of the study

This study primarily aimed to investigate the corporate social responsibility of Nigerian Agip Oil Company for sustainable development among the Ogba people of Rivers State. The specific objectives that guided this study were as follows:

1. Ascertain the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom and Idu.
2. Determine the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom and Idu.
3. Determine the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. To what extent does NAOC CSR on education contribute to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom and Idu?
2. To what extent does NAOC CSR on agriculture contribute to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom and Idu?
3. To what extent does NAOC CSR on infrastructure contribute to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people in Rivers State, Omoku, Obrikom and Idu?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. No significant difference was found in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Rivers State.
2. No significant difference was found in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people in Rivers State.
3. No significant difference was found in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people in Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. This research design was deemed appropriate for the study because the respondents' views or opinions would be elicited and used to provide answers on the variables under investigation.

This study was conducted in the Ogba/Ebgema/Ndoni local government area of Rivers State. The Ogba people are also hosts to NAOC exploration activities, and hence have enjoyed many years of the company's CSR policy implementation. For these reasons the area was chosen for this study.

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. This research design was deemed appropriate for the study because the study's features and characteristics to be reported as they are without manipulating the independent or dependent variable.

This study was conducted in communities in the Ogba/Ebgbema/Ndoni local government area of Rivers State, where NAOC operates. The registered organizations in the population comprised 385 youths from the Idu, Obrikom, and Omoku communities, 105 community development committee members, and 204 council chiefs. The sample size of the study was made up of the entire population of 694 Ogba people. Purposive sampling technique was used for selecting the sample. The selection criteria were, that the members were indigenes of Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu and belonged to either the youth bodies, CDC, or the listed councils of chiefs. These sets of stakeholders are considered most relevant because they directly or indirectly affect NAOC CSR policies and their implementation in host communities.

The data for this research were collected using a structured questionnaire tagged "Corporate Social Responsibility of NAOC for Sustainable Development among the Ogba people Questionnaire (CSRNAOCSDOPQ)" by a researcher. The instrument was made up of 22 items, with research questions 1 and 2 having eight items each and research question 3 having six items. The response options to items were designed based on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE, 4 points), High Extent (HE, 3 points), Low Extent (LE, 2 points), and Very Low Extent (VLE, 1 point).

The designed instrument for data collection was subjected to face validation by three experts. Two of the experts were selected from the Department of Adult Education and Community Studies and one expert from the Field of Measurement and Evaluation, all from Rivers State University. The experts were requested to assess the clarity of the items, the simplicity of the vocabulary, and the relevance of the items in providing the appropriate data for the study. The experts' corrections were considered when producing the final copies of the questionnaire administered to the respondents.

The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's alpha coefficient based on data obtained from 20 members of the Egbema CDC, the youth association, and the council of chiefs in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Council, Rivers State, who were not part of the main study. Reliability testing was performed to test the internal consistency of the instrument. The computation was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 24.0. The computation gave a coefficient of 0.76.

For data collection, the researcher approached the secretary of the Council of Chiefs and president of each of the youth bodies used in this study to serve as assistants for data collection. The purpose of the study was discussed with the secretary and presidents before handing over some copies of the questionnaire to them for onward distribution to their members. The researcher returned after a period of two weeks to collect the filled copies of the questionnaire. Each of the returned copies of the questionnaire was coded to form the study data. Notably, out of the entire 694 copies distributed, only 653 copies were retrieved and filled properly, accounting for approximately 94% of the distributed copies.

To answer the research questions, the data obtained for this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level computed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science version 24.0.

Results/Discussion

Research Question 1: To what extent does NAOC CSR on education contribute to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu?

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on the Extent of NAOC CSR on Education Contributes to Sustainable Educational Development Among Ogba People

S/N	Items	Omoku (n = 376)			Obrikom (n = 154)			Idu (n = 123)		
		Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	NAOC education scholarships to their host communities help meet the needs of the present and future generations	3.35	0.52	HE	3.37	0.51	HE	3.37	0.52	HE
2	The NAOC skills acquisition curriculum helps to address the non-formal education needs of present and future competencies of host communities.	3.15	0.69	HE	3.16	0.72	HE	3.17	0.71	HE
3	NAOC CSR provides educational supplies, such as books, pen, pencils, and bags, to encourage children in host communities to enroll in schools.	3.14	0.67	HE	3.22	0.66	HE	3.22	0.65	HE
4	NAOC skills acquisition programs are designed to address the present and future needs of members of host communities.	3.00	0.77	HE	3.07	0.75	HE	3.08	0.78	HE
5	NAOC consults with stakeholders to design non-formal education aimed at addressing the needs of present and future adults within their host communities.	3.13	0.60	HE	3.19	0.66	HE	3.21	0.67	HE
6	NAOC educational interventions help train teachers of host communities on modern teaching approaches	3.19	0.76	HE	3.30	0.78	HE	3.35	0.75	HE
7	NAOC donates digital infrastructure to schools through its CSR to enable 21st-century educational delivery	3.26	0.73	HE	3.34	0.73	HE	3.36	0.74	HE
8	NAOC has contributed significantly to sustainable educational facilities for the educational development of host communities.	3.17	0.73	HE	3.11	0.76	HE	3.02	0.75	HE
	Average of the Means and Standard Deviations	3.17	0.68	HE	3.22	0.70	HE	3.22	0.70	HE

Source: Field Survey of 2024

Table 1 shows that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom and Idu opined that to a high extent, the NAOC CSR on education scholarships to their host communities are helping to meet the present and future generation's needs; NAOC skills acquisition curriculum helps to address non-formal education need of present and future competencies need of host communities; NAOC CSR provides educational supplies such as books, pen, pencils and bags to encourage host communities children to enroll in schools; NAOC skills acquisition programmes are designed to address present and future needs of host communities' members; NAOC consults with stakeholders to design non-formal education aimed at addressing the need of present and future adults within their host communities; NAOC educational interventions help to train teachers of host communities schools on modern approaches to teaching; NAOC donates digital infrastructure through its CSR to schools to enable 21st century educational delivery; and NAOC has contributed significantly to sustainable educational facilities for the purpose of educational development of host communities with mean scores of 3.35, 3.37, 3.37, 3.15, 3.16, 3.17, 3.14, 3.22, 3.22, 3.00, 3.07, 3.08, 3.13, 3.19, 3.21, 3.19, 3.30, 3.35, 3.26, 3.34, 3.36, 3.17, 3.11, 3.02, and standard deviation scores of 0.52, 0.51, 0.52, 0.69, 0.72, 0.71, 0.67, 0.66, 0.65, 0.77, 0.75, 0.78, 0.60, 0.66, 0.67, 0.76, 0.78, 0.75, 0.73, 0.73, 0.74, 0.73, 0.76, and 0.75 respectively. Similarly, when the average of the mean scores of 3.17, 3.22, and 3.22 and average of standard deviation scores of 0.68, 0.70, and 0.70 for all the Ogba people used in this study are considered, it can be concluded that the people opined that NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does NAOC CSR on agriculture contribute to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu?

Table 2: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on the Extent of NAOC CSR on Agriculture Contributes to Sustainable Agricultural Development Among Ogba People

S/N	Items	Omoku (n=376)			Obrikom (n = 154)			Idu (n = 123)		
		Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
9	NAOC agricultural development interventions guide members of host communities on how to improve soil fertility to meet the needs of the present and future generations.	3.11	0.48	HE	3.14	0.46	HE	3.14	0.47	HE
10	NAOC agricultural intervention provides host communities with eco-friendly seedlings and plants to preserve land nutrients	3.50	0.63	VHE	3.41	0.64	HE	3.37	0.63	HE
11	The NAOC Green Rivers project assists farmers in host communities with input resources for crop production to meet current and future food security needs.	3.09	0.65	HE	3.21	0.62	HE	3.24	0.59	HE
13	NAOC Green Rivers equip farmers in host communities with agricultural practices that can improve their yields.	3.29	0.71	HE	3.37	0.72	HE	3.42	0.72	HE
13	NAOC Green Rivers train farmers in host communities on how to add value to their agricultural outcomes to meet current and future needs.	3.15	0.73	HE	3.09	0.74	HE	3.04	0.75	HE

14	NAOC agricultural intervention programs empower members of host communities to engage in fish farming, poultry, and other agricultural ventures.	3.25	0.71	HE	3.44	0.69	HE	3.51	0.63	VHE
15	NAOC uses its resources to teach non-toxic and low-energy farming practices for improved yields to members of host communities interested in farming.	3.11	0.60	HE	3.07	0.50	HE	3.06	0.45	HE
16	NAOC provides community farmers with training on how to add value to their products to ensure food security.	3.35	0.72	HE	3.38	0.65	HE	3.39	0.60	HE
	Average of the Means and Standard Deviations	3.22	0.65	HE	3.26	0.63	HE	3.27	0.61	HE

Source: Field Survey of 2024

Table 2 reveals that Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom and Idu opined that to a high extent NAOC agricultural development interventions guide members of host communities on how to improve on soil fertility to meet the needs of the present and future generations; NAOC Green Rivers project assists host communities’ farmers with inputs resources for crops production to meet current and future food security needs; NAOC Green Rivers equips host communities farmers with agricultural practices capable of improving their yields; NAOC Green Rivers trains host communities farmers on how to add value to their agricultural outcomes to meet current and future needs; NAOC uses its resources to teach members of host community interested in farming on non-toxic and low energy farming practices for improved yields; and NAOC provides farmers within the community with training on how to add value to their products to ensure food security with mean scores of 3.11, 3.14, 3.14, 3.09, 3.21, 3.24, 3.29, 3.37, 3.42, 3.15, 3.09, 3.04, 3.11, 3.07, 3.06, 3.35, 3.38, 3.39 and standard deviation scores of 0.48, 0.46, 0.47, 0.65, 0.62, 0.59, 0.71, 0.72, 0.72, 0.73, 0.74, 0.75, 0.60, 0.50, 0.45, 0.72, 0.65, and 0.60 respectively. However, the Ogba people from Omoku opined that NAOC agricultural intervention provides host communities with eco-friendly seedlings and plants to preserve the land nutrients to a very high extent with a mean score of 3.50 and a standard deviation score of 0.63, while their counterparts from Obrikom and Idu opined that the same intervention by NAOC provides host communities with eco-friendly seedlings and plants to preserve the land nutrients with mean scores of 3.41, 3.37, and standard deviation scores of 0.64 and 0.63, respectively. Similarly, the Ogba people from Idu opined that NAOC agricultural intervention programs empower members of host communities to a very high extent on fish farming, poultry, and other agricultural ventures with a mean score of 3.51 and standard deviation score of 0.63, while their counterparts from Omoku and Obrikom opined that the same happens to a high extent with mean scores of 3.25 and 3.44 and standard deviation scores of 0.71 and 0.69, respectively. Nevertheless, when the average of all the mean scores at 3.22, 3.26, and 3.27 and the average of the standard deviation scores at 0.65, 0.63, and 0.61 are considered, it can be concluded that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does NAOC CSR on infrastructure contribute to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on the Extent of NAOC CSR on Infrastructure Contributions to Sustainable Educational Development Among Ogba People

S/N	Items	Omoku (n = 376)			Obrikom (n = 154)			Idu (n = 123)		
		Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
17	NAOC CSR on infrastructure ensures infrastructural need assessments within host communities before interventions are given to make the members see the projects' relevance in their sustainable development.	3.14	0.74	HE	3.18	0.79	HE	3.11	0.80	HE
18	NAOC has significantly financed the construction of physical infrastructure in host communities, such as roads, drainages, water boreholes, schools, community centers, and local markets.	3.10	0.68	HE	3.09	0.76	HE	3.11	0.78	HE
19	NAOC is involved in monitoring the construction of physical infrastructures to ensure the quality delivery of roads, drainages, water boreholes, schools, community centers, and local markets in host communities.	3.33	0.65	HE	3.35	0.65	HE	3.37	0.65	HE
28	NAOC involvement in the efficient utilization of available local resources to enhance community infrastructure and ensure the actualization of sustainable community development projects.	3.21	0.62	HE	3.33	0.67	HE	3.38	0.66	HE
20	NAOC involvement in community infrastructure renovations from time to time to ensure sustainability	3.24	0.65	HE	3.29	0.60	HE	3.28	0.60	HE
21	NAOC involvement in physical infrastructure innovation ensures the sustainability of community development projects.	3.12	0.67	HE	3.21	0.68	HE	3.29	0.65	HE
	Average of the Means and Standard Deviations	3.19	0.67	HE	3.24	0.69	HE	3.26	0.69	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 reveals that Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom and Idu opined that to a high extent NAOC CSR on infrastructure ensures infrastructural need assessments within host communities before interventions are given to make the members see the relevance of the projects in their sustainable development; NAOC has significantly finance the construction of physical infrastructures such as road, drainages, water boreholes, schools, community centres, and local markets in host communities; NAOC is involved in monitoring the construction of physical infrastructures it finance in order to ensure quality delivery of road, drainages, water boreholes, schools, community centres, and local markets in host communities; NAOC involvement in efficient utilization of

available local resources to enhance community infrastructure and ensures the actualization of sustainable community development projects; NAOC involvement in community infrastructure renovations from time to time in order to ensure their sustainability; and NAOC involvement in physical infrastructure innovation helps to ensure sustainability of community development projects with mean scores of 3.14, 3.18, 3.11, 3.10, 3.09, 3.11, 3.33, 3.35, 3.37, 3.21, 3.33, 3.38, 3.24, 3.29, 3.28, 3.12, 3.21, 3.29 and standard deviation scores of 0.74, 0.79, 0.80, 0.68, 0.76, 0.78, 0.65, 0.65, 0.65, 0.62, 0.67, 0.66, 0.65, 0.60, 0.60, 0.67, 0.68 and 0.65 respectively. In the same vein, when the average of the mean scores of 3.19, 3.24, and 3.26 and average of standard deviation scores of 0.67, 0.69, and 0.69 are considered, it can be concluded that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development to a high extent.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Variance on Significant Difference in the Mean Rating of Respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba People

	Sum of the Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	22.24	2	11.12	2.66	.07
Within Groups	2715.08	650	4.18		
Total	2737.32	652			

Table 4 shows that the sum of squares between groups is 22.24, with 2 as the degree of freedom and mean square of 11.12. The table also shows that the within-group sum of squares is 2715.08 and 650 degrees of freedom, as well as a mean square of 4.18. The total has 2737.32 sum of squares and 652 degrees of freedom. The computed F ratio is 2.66, which is a statistically insignificant alpha of 0.07. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people, is accepted; $F(2, 650) = 2.66, p > 0.05$ at 0.07. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people.

Table 5: Summary of Analysis of Variance on Significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people

	Sum of the Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	14.64	2	7.32	2.09	.12
Within Groups	2273.81	650	3.50		
Total	2288.45	652			

Table 5 shows that the sum of squares between groups is 14.64, with 2 as the degree of freedom and mean square of 7.32. The table also shows that the within-group sum of squares is 2273.81 and 650 degrees of freedom, as

well as a mean square of 3.50. The total has 2288.45 sum of squares and 652 degrees of freedom. The computed F ratio is 2.09, which is not statistically significant at alpha 0.12. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people, is accepted; $F(2, 650) = 2.09, p > 0.05$ at 0.12. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people.

Table 6: Summary of Analysis of Variance on Significant Difference in the Mean Rating of Respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba People

	Sum of the Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18.78	2	9.39	2.96	.05
Within Groups	2063.51	650	3.18		
Total	2082.30	652			

Table 6 shows that the sum of squares between groups is 18.78, with 2 as the degree of freedom and mean square of 9.39. The table also shows that the within-group sum of squares is 2063.51 and 650 degrees of freedom, as well as a mean square of 3.18. The total has 2082.30 sum of squares and 652 degrees of freedom. The computed F ratio is 2.96, which is not statistically significant at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people, is accepted; $F(2, 650) = 2.96, p > 0.05$ at 0.05. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people.

Discussion of the Major Findings

The discussion of the major findings is conducted under each of the specific objectives they addressed:

The extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu:

The results related to this specific purpose revealed that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development to a high extent. The results of the test of hypothesis relating to this purpose showed no significant difference in the mean rating of Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on education contributes to sustainable educational development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu. This finding was based on the fact that respondents from stakeholders in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined to a high extent on NAOC CSR on education scholarships to their host communities, NAOC skills acquisition curriculum promoted through its CSR initiative helps to address non-formal education need, NAOC CSR provides educational supplies such as books, pen, pencils, and bags to encourage host communities children to enroll in schools; NAOC skills acquisition programs, NAOC consultation with stakeholders to design non-formal education, NAOC educational interventions in training teachers of host communities schools on modern approaches to teaching; NAOC donation of digital infrastructure through its CSR to schools; and NAOC contribution to educational facilities,

significantly addresses the educational needs of the present and future generations. The findings of this study are supported by Roorda (2019), who affirmed that the essence of CSR on education is to ensure that holistic, inclusive, and transformative education systems are capable of empowering individuals to participate in strengthening communities and contributing more to a sustainable and equitable world. The findings of this study are also supported by Olawuyi (2021), who noted that CSR on educational programs is culturally relevant, ensuring language preservation and the inclusion of diverse values, guaranteeing respect for the dignity of all by eliminating gender disparities with regard to access to education.

The extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu:

The results related to this specific purpose revealed that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development to a high extent. The results of the test of the hypothesis related to this specific purpose also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on agriculture contributes to sustainable agricultural development. This finding emanated from the fact that respondents from the stakeholders in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that to a high extent, NAOC agricultural development interventions guide members of host communities on how to improve soil fertility. The NAOC Green Rivers project assists host communities' farmers with input resources for crop production, and NAOC Green Rivers equips farmers with agricultural practices capable of improving their yields. NAOC Green Rivers trains farmers on how to add value to their agricultural outcomes. NAOC uses its resources to teach members of host communities interested in farming on non-toxic and low-energy farming practices for improved yields. NAOC provides farmers within the community with training on how to add value to their products to ensure food security in the present and the future. The findings of this study are supported by the findings of Nedeia (2021), who noted that private sector intervention for sustainable agricultural development in communities of operations is meant to guarantee the local people's food and protein needs while not compromising the needs of those who will come. The finding is also supported by the assertion of Adadi (2021) who noted that CSR policies for sustainable agricultural development mostly drive the adoption and use of comprehensive and integrated approaches, which are considered to have positive economic, social, and environmental implications because they promote processes leading to improved agricultural services, quality, and quantity yields to ensure the present and future generations' food security.

The extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development among Ogba people in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu:

The results relating to this specific purpose revealed that the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development to a high extent. The results of hypothesis testing related to this specific purpose also revealed no significant difference in the mean rating of Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu on the extent to which NAOC CSR on infrastructure contributes to sustainable infrastructural development. This finding emanated from the fact that the respondents from the stakeholders in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu opined that to a high extent, NAOC CSR on infrastructure ensures infrastructural need assessments within host communities before interventions are given to make the members see the relevance of the projects. NAOC has significantly financed the construction of physical infrastructures such as roads, drainages, water boreholes, schools, community centers, and local markets in host communities. NAOC is involved in monitoring the construction of physical infrastructures it finances to ensure quality delivery. NAOC is involved in the efficient utilization of available local resources to enhance community

infrastructure. NAOC is involved with community infrastructure renovations from time to time to ensure their sustainability. NAOC is involved in physical infrastructure innovation to help ensure the sustainability of community development projects. The findings of this study are supported by Babatunde et al. (2011), who reported that CSR on infrastructural development has evolved as a paradigm to ensure the provision of basic amenities that meet the developmental needs of human society and engender community development. The findings of this study are also supported by Anvuur (2018), who noted that sustainable infrastructural development through CSR is ensured through effective planning, design, and implementation of initiatives that lead to the construction and operation of physical structures and systems that support social equity and economic development over the long term.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that NAOC CSR on education, agriculture, and infrastructure of their host communities in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu to a high extent contributed to sustainable community development proxies such as sustainable educational, agricultural, and infrastructural development. It was also concluded that no significant difference exists in the extent to which NAOC CSR contributes to sustainable community development in the Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu communities. Therefore, these conclusions suggest that the various communities in Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu have been witnessing certain improvements in their educational, agricultural, and infrastructure, which are addressing the needs of the present members and would also cater to the needs of the future generations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu, through their stakeholders such as community development committee members, youth bodies, and council of chiefs, should lobby to ensure that oil firms' subsequent CSR on education within their environment focuses on areas that would enhance the extent of contributions to sustainable educational development among their communities.
2. Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu should canvass for more sustainable agricultural development initiatives in the CSR on agriculture proposed for implementation by the firms through their various community stakeholders that interact on their behalf with oil firms within their areas.
3. Through their various stakeholders, the Ogba people from Omoku, Obrikom, and Idu should canvass with the directors of CSR of oil firms within their areas to provide for more enhanced CSR on infrastructure capable of enhancing the extent of its contribution to sustainable infrastructural development among their communities.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, P. U. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Human Rights Accountability in Nigerian Petroleum Industry: From Voluntarism to Legal Positivism. *US-China Law Review*, 17, (6), 250-260.
- Bagdasaryan, A. (2016). Implementation of CSR policies by Russian oil companies. This thesis was submitted for the award of Bachelor of Business Administration to KYAMK University of Applied Sciences, Russia.
- Dan-Moller, H. (2020). Assessing a farm's sustainability: insights from resilience thinking *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 8 (3), 186- 198.
- Drakakis-Smith, D. (2021). Third-World Cities: Sustainable Urban Infrastructural Development *Urban Studies*, 32(5), 659-677.

- Gbali, K. C., Weli, V. E., & Mmom, P. C. (2021). Corporate social responsibilities of international oil companies as a panacea for conflict management in selected host communities in southern Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, Vol. 11, No. 03, pp. 351–362.
- Hailsham, S. F. L., & Dokubo, C. & Deekor, L. H. (2021). Influence of corporate social responsibility of Exxon Mobil Nigeria unlimited on community develop in Rivers State/*International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 9 (1). 38-49
- James, U. (2016). Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria-People and the environment. *Journal of Petroleum Development*. Annual Report, 20-30.
- Joe, D. & Kechi, K. (2013). Implications of CSR for Nigerian Firms *Advances in Management and Applied Economics*, 3(5): 78-87.
- Kornom-Gbaraba, M. E. & Aernan, J. E. (2021). Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Costs on the Financial Performance of Oil Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research* 9(1):109-117
- Mahoney, L., & Roberts, R. W. (2019). Corporate Social Performance, Financial Performance and Institutional Ownership in Canadian Firms, 31, 233–53.
- Masi, D. (2019). Message from the management of the stakeholders and the community development division manager. *Sustainability newsletter*, 5 (3). 8–9
- McMichael, A. J. (2020). Powles, J. W., Butler, C. D., & Uauy, R. (2007). "Food, livestock production, energy, climate change, and health. *The Lancet*. 370 (9594): 1253–1263.
- Roorda, N. (2019). AISHE–Assessment Instrument for Sustainability in Higher Education. Stichting Duurzaam Hoger Onderwijs (DHO),
- United Nations Industrial Development Organization (2024). Corporate Social Responsibility. <https://www.unido.org/our-focus/advancing-economic-competitiveness/competitive-trade-capacities-and-corporate-responsibility/corporate-social-responsibility-market-integration/what-csr#:~:text=Corporate%20Social%20Responsibility%20is%20a,and%20interactions%20with%20their%20stakeholders>.
- Victor, T. & Okpu, T. O. (2021). Corporate Social Responsibility: A Study of Factors influencing Host Community Perception and Expectations of Oil Companies in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 23(4),11-17
- Victor, T. (2021). Corporate Social Responsibility: A Study of Factors Influencing Host Community Perception and Expectations of Oil Companies in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 23(04), 11-17.

Zhao, W. (2015). Corporate Social Responsibility in the Energy Industry: A Content Analysis of the Websites of Leading Energy Companies. Electronic Theses, Treatises and Dissertations submitted to The Graduate School, Florida State University Libraries.